

APPLICATION OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING STUDENT INDEPENDENT WORK

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Abstract. *The use of targeted information computer technologies in the organization of the student's independent learning process in the subject provides technical and technological support to the teacher, saves a lot of time for live communication with students, as a result of which communication with students takes place in a human and individual way, in a close relationship, in the form of master-apprentice.*

Keywords: *Independent learning, student's independent work, pedagogical technology.*

Along with lectures, practical classes, and seminars, students' independent work plays an important role in mastering the curriculum. Consequently, the organization of this form of education and the application of new pedagogical technologies in this process have their own peculiarities. Students' independent work should supplement the materials of lectures and practical classes without repetition, and further clarify certain issues. Taking this requirement into account, at the beginning of the academic year, a list of topics for independent work will be developed for each lesson in the disciplines taught at the department - forensic medicine and medical law. For each topic, the objects and types of independent work are determined.

In particular, in addition to preparing a report, a slide presentation on a typical topic in forensic medicine, participating in a forensic medical examination of a corpse or living person and compiling a forensic medical diagnosis, an expert opinion, students may be assigned the task of creating various versions of schematic organizers based on new pedagogical technologies, developing a set of tests of varying complexity on new situational problems or a specific issue in the form of independent work. In this case, students not only become acquainted with new material, but also develop skills in generalizing and analyzing the obtained information. At the present time, in the context of the democratization and humanization of society, the expansion of human rights and freedoms, it is very important to educate the younger generation capable of independent activity. Independence, initiative, creativity, purposefulness - these are important qualities of the modern human personality, necessary for the formation of an independent opinion of a person, for improving and developing independent solutions, decisions on vital problems now and in the future. In modern conditions, creative activity and independence are characteristic of a modern specialist. Independent work

of a student should not be considered as a simple method of acquiring knowledge, on the contrary, it is one of the main principles of the activities of a higher educational institution. Independent learning is a necessary component of the unified educational process, as it is organized, purposefully directed, regulated, and controlled by the educational process. Therefore, the organization of students' independent work, especially in the context of the development of information and communication technologies, is one of the most important and effective directions for improving the quality of education. It is known that active learning and scientific research activity require the effective use of all types of independent research. The student's independent work should manifest itself in all forms of the educational process. The main goal of independent student work is the formation and development of the necessary knowledge and skills in the student to independently perform certain educational work under the guidance and supervision of the teacher.

Naturally, when considering the basic principles of guiding and organizing students' independent work, great attention should be paid to the formation and development of students' solid skills in independent work with educational and scientific literature. As a conclusion. As a result of the use of new computerized information technologies, the educational process becomes individualized, new motives appear in students in mastering subjects, feedback plays a strong role in the student-teacher system, the objectivity of knowledge assessment increases, the collection of statistical data becomes easier, some aspects of knowledge acquisition (good, low) are clearly manifested in students, the teacher has the opportunity to change the structure of the lesson (in accordance with the level of initial training of students), allows differentiating the educational process, increases the level of mastery of the topic, the subject, and increases interest in it. The use of computer technologies in the educational process provides technical and technological support to the teacher, significantly saves time for live communication with students, as a result of which communication with students takes place in a human and individual way, in a close relationship, in the form of master-apprentice.

Literature

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